

INCULTUM – Visiting the margins

Antonella Fresa
Promoter S.r.l.
Peccioli, Italy
fresa@promoter.it,

Pietro Masi
masi@promoter.it

Elisa Debernardi
debernardi@promoter.it

Abstract

INCULTUM is an Innovation Action funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 Programme. The project is focused on novel approaches to urban and regional development through cultural tourism, with the aim of furthering sustainable social, cultural and economic development. It aims to explore the full potential of marginal and peripheral areas when managed by local communities and stakeholders. Innovative participatory approaches are tested in a wide range of Pilots where local communities are transformed into protagonists, adopting digital and participatory solutions. The results of the Pilots are promoted as good practices to be replicated and translated into strategies and policies.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is more than travelling and consuming, and it has a great potential for sustainable development when it focuses on culture, nature, knowledge, and experiences. Travelling is a way to learn and improve oneself, to enrich the vision of the world and to improve the understanding of the others. Travelling is a discovery that satisfies our inherent curiosity and, in some ways, provides us with a romantic sense of adventure, the need to explore and go beyond. Tourism has become one of the most important industries and economic activities in the world, with impacts on culture, social relationships and environment, and it can be considered one of the key elements of globalization. However, the increase of tourism is a global phenomenon that is not always based on those ideas. Tourism has also become a problem because of a negative impact at different levels. Touristification is one of the negative consequences in many historical cities, protected natural areas and coastal regions. Widespread growth and gathering of people cause problems for the local population, such as gentrification, insecurity of employment, social changes, and massive urbanization. Additionally, touristification reduces the quality of the visitor experience. Crowded monuments, historical city centres or beaches result in long waiting times and prevent visitors to enjoy the visit. Tourism is frequently related to consumerism, including many critical offers in rural areas and natural environments.

The INCULTUM project [1] intends to demonstrate a new concept of cultural tourism, based on participation, authenticity, and digital interaction as a response for limiting the negative impacts that touristification implies. The adoption of innovative participatory approaches to promote cultural tourism can become a driver for growth and sustainable economic development in local communities. Furthermore, the use of the digital technologies can unlock new opportunities for the encounter of visitors and residents, offering opportunities of interaction and exchanges. Within this new concept, marginal and peripheral places can express their full potential, cultural heritage and

natural resources are more protected and preserved, and local communities and stakeholders can become actors playing concrete roles in driving the direction of development of their territory.

EXPERIMENTING PARTICIPATORY MODELS FOR SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

INCULTUM plans to go beyond the classical concept of cultural tourism in over-exploited areas, and aims to reach the margins of deprived, remote, peripheral or deindustrialized areas that in one way or another lag behind. 'Incultum' is the Latin word that means uncultivated, untilled, neglected and in this light the project is focused on 'uncultivated' cultural and natural heritage, as well as authentic and not much known local production, to show the values of the most attractive elements of a hidden Europe. INCULTUM aims to demonstrate the potential of these marginal and peripheral places, by supporting strategies for a sustainable and authentic cultural tourism.

Ten Pilot cases are selected for the INCULTUM's innovation action, covering a wide range of contexts, partners, associated partners and stakeholders, in different European geographic areas, representing various shades of the European 'incultum'. Some of the Pilots are part of European cultural routes or can be linked to them. The ten Pilot cases of INCULTUM represent important examples of European history, memory and landscapes: from agrarian practices and traditional ecological knowledge to small and isolated cemeteries, from traditional gastronomy to conflictive borders or isolated areas that are quiet but full of life. There, we can still discover and bring to life essential and authentic parts of Europe's heritage, respectful of the local communities.

In the various kinds of cultural tourism, two or more collective identities meet and interact: the local people (citizens and stakeholders) and the visitors. It is a distinct goal of INCULTUM that none of these social identities suffers unwanted changes. The project aims to make sure that the social identities involved are only positively affected, increasing pride in local heritage, forms of production, traditions, and natural scenery. In the project's view, this is a promising way to counter the negative and often denaturalising effects of tourism, where locals stop doing what they used to do in order to cater for tourists instead. To this end, the project measures the cultural and social value perception related to the social identities in each of the Pilot sites, to develop corrective measures in case of detection of negative impacts.

The use of digital content to create virtual paths is an important element to promote the territories, providing information to the visitors about the history of the places, before, during and after their travelling. To this regard, accessing valuable digital repositories of cultural contents, including photographs, videos and 3D representations is experimented in the Pilots. Dedicated inventories and mapping of cultural resources, accessible via specific digital services are produced by the INCULTUM partners in relation to their territories.

The Pilot cases are the places for INCULTUM to develop innovative strategies for the development of sustainable tourism strategies, to be elaborated together with stakeholders, local administrations and policy makers. Bottom-up approaches are fostered, focusing on hidden and undervalued potentialities usually not taken into account, and on the experience, learning and participation of visitors. Promotion of cultural tourism is based on the living experiences of the local communities in their territories, avoiding negative impacts of touristification. Specific training are designed aiming at reinforcing local identities and social ties. Finally, an important phase of the project is to evaluate the impact of the interventions Piloted in the project, on the social cohesion, highlighting local identity, and using various measures of life satisfaction in the local communities.

The selection of the Pilots to be included in the innovation experiment was based on prioritising deprived, remote, peripheral and deindustrialized areas or cultural-natural heritage not usually taken into account by the mainstream tourism processes. All the Pilots are based on existing studies with

previous experiences in the selected areas, even if covering also other domains beyond cultural tourism. The ten Pilot cases cover a variety of contexts being developed in nine different countries: Spain, Portugal, Italy, France, Greece, Albania, Ireland and Sweden. From North to South and from East to West, the INCULTUM innovations are experimented in a broad range of cases across Europe, in different geographical locations, with a diversity of socio-economic situations, representing many kinds of cultural-natural heritage, including relevant cross-border significance.

Geographical distribution of the INCULTUM Pilots

Legenda:

1. Spain
2. Portugal
3. Slovakia
4. Italy (Trapani Mountains)
5. Italy (Garfagnana Appennine)
6. France
7. Greece
8. Albania
9. Ireland
10. Sweden

The Pilot in Spain is located on the Altiplano de Granada, on the Sierra Nevada, and it deals with desert landscapes and oasis. It is a flat semi-arid area with poor soils and an extreme climate due to its altitude, continental influence and the presence of surrounding mountains. These characteristics

have contributed to the creation of a unique landscape marked by impressive badlands where the historical relationship between humans and the environment has built balances based on a sustainable use of resources, particularly water and soils. This has allowed the creation of historical irrigation systems, strongly influenced by Islamic presence, which form real oases of great beauty with numerous cultural and environmental values.

The Pilot in Portugal is located at Campina de Faro, part of the coastal plain on the littoral of Algarve, in the south of Portugal. Situated on an aquifer and fertile soils, it is still, despite urban-touristic pressure, a living testimony of the historical interdependence between the cities and the food production space (gardens, orchards) based on the traditional irrigation system now in the process of being abandoned. The Pilot action is directed towards survey, diagnosis and architectural and hydraulic rehabilitation of a group of norias, aqueducts and tanks in order to contribute to the preservation of the landscape's memory and to the (re)activation of its identity.

The Pilot in Slovakia deals with the mining treasures of Central Slovakia including the mining cities of Banská Bystrica and Banská Štiavnica (UNESCO World Heritage Site). The proposed Pilot is a cross-cutting action within two tourism routes – the Barbora Route and the European Fugger Route. The Barbora Route passes through the most significant mining sites and monuments associated with the mining tradition throughout the region of the former Central Slovak mining towns. The European Fugger Route (Fuggerstrasse) takes visitors to silver and copper mines in Austria, Germany, Italy and Slovakia, where the Fugger family made their fortune. Although the Banská Bystrica region plays an important role in both routes, the city significantly lacks marketing and digital tools promoting this unique part of its history.

Two Pilots are running in Italy. One is located in the Sicilian inland, on the Mountains of Trapani, a land rich of Islamic traces. The Pilot focuses on the creation of cultural routes based on agricultural and archaeological heritage. The other Italian Pilot is located on the Tuscan-Emilian Apennines, at San Pellegrino in Alpe, the highest permanently inhabited area in the whole Apennine chain that constituted, since the Middle Ages, a passage for pilgrims and merchants. Here the Pilot action targets both at cultural tourism operators and hiking guides in order to create a continuum between culture and nature that optimally represents the territory and its potential.

The Pilot in France is located at Bibracte, in the area of the massif of Morvan, in central-eastern France, site of a 1st c. BC fortified town, part of the national policy of the Grands Sites de France. Bibracte acts as a testing ground for Regional Natural Park of Morvan, within the framework of the Grand Site de France policy conducted by the Ministry in charge of the environment and landscapes [2].

The Pilots in Greece and in Albania are located in the two sides of the river called Aaos in Greece and Vjosa in Albania. The river is considered as one of Europe's last living wild rivers, it springs from Mt. Pindus in Greece, enters Albania at the border crossing point of Tre Urat (Three Bridges), and continues up to the Gorge of Këlcyra, which defines the northern extreme of the Upper Vjosa Valley. The natural and cultural resources of the Greek Pilot are mapped on a digital platform [3] that is accessible via the INCULTUM website.

The Pilot in Ireland refers to the whole territory of the Republic of Ireland and is based on the use of the online platform Historic Graves [4]. Referring to the Irish diaspora, the historical process of migration from Ireland recorded since the Early Middle Ages, the Historic Graves initiative started in 2010, as a community-focused participatory grassroots heritage project. Local community groups living in Ireland are trained in low-cost high-tech field survey of historic graveyards, recording their own oral histories. The online platform gathered together a worldwide community of more than 15,000 users, collaborating in generating a nationwide genealogical dataset.

The Pilot in Sweden runs in rural and peri-urban areas in the Swedish archipelago and in the territory of the great lakes. This unique landscape offers a number of coastal areas for recreation,

whose development can contribute to a more evenly distribution of tourists between urban and rural areas.

In addition to the cross-border Pilots in Albania and Greece, also the Pilots in Portugal, Sicily and Spain represent a group of cross-border Pilots. While the Pilots in Albania and Greece have a geographical connected territory, where they look at re-discovering similarities as well as pointing out cultural specificities, the group of cross-border Pilots in Portugal, Sicily and Spain have a cultural-historic element of liaison, i.e. the common traces of Islamic heritage, with particular regard to the irrigation systems that are still visible in those regions.

STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING

INCULTUM is founded upon the central idea that an untapped potential exists in sustainable cultural tourism. This is completely in line with the EU policies on the subject, which aim to promote cultural tourism balancing the need for growth and development with preservation of cultural heritage, historical sites, and local traditions. INCULTUM follows the definition of cultural tourism made by the World Tourism Organisation (UNWTO) as *“a type of tourism activity in which the visitor’s essential motivation is to learn, discover, experience and consume the tangible and intangible cultural attractions/products in a tourism destination. These attractions/products relate to a set of distinctive material, intellectual, spiritual and emotional features of a society that encompasses arts and architecture, historical and cultural heritage, culinary heritage, literature, music, creative industries and the living cultures with their lifestyles, value systems, beliefs and traditions”* [5].

The UNWTO’s definition includes both local residents and tourists. In this light, at least two groups – i.e. locals and visitors -, each one with their own collective identity, meet and interact in a way that each of them is only positively affected. On one hand, they are expected to improve awareness and pride in local heritage, and, on the other hand, the experience aims at fomenting the visitors’ curiosity and knowledge about the destination in all its aspects. In our view, this is important to counter the negative, and often denaturalising, effects of touristification specifically, and of tourism in general. The risk may be even larger in areas suffering from unemployment, underdevelopment, and depopulation, since locals may be more tempted in such areas to stop doing what they were used to do because they can earn more by catering for tourists. By experimenting in the Pilots a range of innovations in cultural tourism based on participatory approaches, engagement of local communities, and smart use of digital technologies, INCULTUM aims to demonstrate the positive impact of these innovations at social, cultural, environmental and economic levels.

The point is to increase the awareness that the demand side – i.e. the market for cultural tourism – and the supply side – i.e. the local economic and social development – depend on each other. The synergies created by INCULTUM focus on both the local level as well as on the cultural tourists – both actual and prospective. In facts, cultural tourism simply cannot happen without tourists visiting the Pilot areas.

Three levels of actions are validated in the INCULTUM project. The principal validation takes place at the local/regional level related to the ten INCULTUM Pilots, in the framework of the activities undertaken therein. Secondly, the project encourages a cross-fertilisation between the Pilots. This means that – whenever possible – each Pilot serves as the first testing ground of the solutions that the other Pilots implement. Naturally, such cross-fertilisation is based on a relevance criterion, even if we expect that many aspects of innovation could be relevant to various other Pilots. Thirdly, the Pilot solutions are spread among the wider network of interested stakeholders created through a dedicated networking activity that is carried out in the project. This links will facilitate re-use of good practices and duplication of experiences in new geographical contexts, preparing for further replications in other places beyond the ten locations of the INCULTUM Pilots.

The responsibility of the exploitation of the project's results stays in a dedicated strand of work that monitors the advancement of the validation activities carried out in the INCULTUM Pilots, as well the marketability and up-scaling of the tested solutions. It should be taken into account that the ten Pilots are rather different, both in terms of content and focus as well as in terms of level of maturity. They find themselves at various levels of development: some are already well-established, while others are only at an initial stage. In the latter case, the network of stakeholders is often not fully established yet. The differences between the Pilots and the complexity of the whole project makes it imperative to reflect on how to ensure alignment and coordination between Pilots, but at the same time offers the opportunity to reflect, critically, on a wide range of cases. The stakeholder mapping [6] performed in the early stage of the project precisely serves this aim and is fundamental to prepare for further analysis related to impact and exploitation.

DATA GATHERING AND ANALYSIS TO FEED POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The project carries out place-based participatory approaches and specific strategies for the Pilots, in different geographical, social and cultural contexts to improve cultural tourism through new insights, social innovation, cross border and local cooperation of a wide and diversified partnership of stakeholders. Pilots allow to experiment and to understand better trends and possibilities of sustainable tourism based on local potentialities and capacities, but also on participation in the governance of tourism development. Pilot solutions are tested and qualified so that the experiences can be replicated and adapted, within an effort of capacity building and training for local cultural managers, cultural heritage institutions, academia and other stakeholders in the local touristic promotion. As illustrated in the next chapter, a wide range of digital resources are made available to the various local actors for their training and capacity building, via online access to courses, professional reports and examples of good practices. In addition to all that, a specific research area of the project is devoted to analyse data, representing indicators, trends and patterns that are useful for policy makers and local stakeholders.

INCULTUM aims to produce quantitative and qualitative data on cultural tourism, gathered in the ten Pilots, as well as to take advantage of already existing data, broadly related to the phenomenon. The scope is to produce and implement new and innovative data analysis and statistics, in order to establish convincing relationships between innovation in cultural tourism, and actual evidence of the effect produced on the development of the territories. The INCULTUM Data Workshop took place on 3/3/2022. All the presentations and recording of keynote interventions are available online [7].

State-of-the-art econometric approaches are used with a particular focus on the identification of causal relationships, as opposed to just a correlation. The proposed data gathering and analysis will enable a critical monitoring of the actual contribution delivered by INCULTUM. The relevant socio-cultural dimension that steers the implementation of the Pilots and the development of the new strategies for INCULTUM cultural tourism aims to guarantee a quality contribution to the ongoing process of cultural Europeanisation. Training experiences, innovative use of digital communication, work on data and understanding of the socio-cultural implications are reflected in the policy recommendations produced in the project to support the implementation of participatory models in tourism development, which are widely accepted as a criterion for sustainable tourism. Participatory models tend to move away from top-down one-way decision-making in order to balance the power between all parties to promote a win-win situation in tourism development.

INCULTUM dedicates a specific project activity to policies that directly responds to Agenda 2030 and Sustainable Development Goals, namely Goals 8, 12 and 14 on inclusive and sustainable economic growth, sustainable consumption and production and the sustainable use of oceans and marine resources. In addition, the work aims to contribute to SDG 11 Sustainable cities and

communities, while directly strengthening several targets and indicators. The project activity is oriented towards connectivity between policies, participatory models and innovative tools, including the digital sphere. In particular, the objectives of this activity are to identify different types of participatory models, thereby focusing on positions of the involved actors and the coordination mechanisms that are used predominantly in cultural tourism and re-usable in Pilot actions. Relevant drivers and barriers that account for the success or failure of participatory models are compared. The outcomes of participatory models, that are based on co-creation of innovative tools in relation to the expected benefits for the involved stakeholders, are assessed. The aim is to create and design a Policy Toolbox for Participatory Models in order to reflect drivers and barriers for different participatory models and evaluation framework for their assessment. Finally, policy recommendations are derived, leading to synergies between participatory models and innovative tools arrangements.

TRAINING FOR CAPACITY BUILDING

An important part of INCULTUM is dedicated to promoting capacity building and knowledge, in order to enable the implementation of more advanced cultural tourism approaches that are based on living territories and communities. It will be possible to reduce tourism's negative impact through specific training, strengthening local identities and social ties. In particular, local training is offered to local communities, students, tourism professionals and cultural heritage experts, in the frame of the Pilot activities. The training methodology follows a bottom-up structure, the main purpose being to improve socio-economic and geographical knowledge for a community co-creation design of sustainable tourism destinations.

The combination of online and offline interaction with local communities is a key element in terms of ensuring meaningful participation, local and global community engagement and local empowerment, data sharing and training results.

The INCULTUM Training Portal [8], publicly accessible via the project's website, hosts various types of training resources, either developed within the project or collected from existing good practices. It also enables a fruitful relationship between the INCULTUM Pilots. The Training Portal offers access to different areas. i.e.: training resources for cultural managers, tourism professionals, and students, including courses for social branding and community management; INCULTUM research outcomes, including all scientific publications by the project and the INCULTUM Book; reference to collaborations with other participatory and training initiatives involved with participatory approaches and digital cultural heritage promotion; and finally, a section with useful links and bibliography to guide further research.

In the course of the project, an empirical training session dedicated to Pilots is deployed, offering material for skills development in destination marketing and destination governance, with a participatory local heritage renovation approach in terms of tourism accessibility and local identity rediscovering purpose. The outcomes of the training session are shared with the cultural tourism community. Finally, the INCULTUM training action will be included in the project's final conference to be held in Granada in 2024, for further dissemination and take up of the INCULTUM knowledge and solutions by others.

CONCLUSION

In summary, across its work plan developed during 2021-2024, the INCULTUM project focuses specifically on promoting marginal, hidden and not always highly considered cultural heritage of very diverse typology: agrarian spaces, traditional ecological knowledge and practices, minorities, identity places like historical graveyards, mining-industrial heritage, depopulated areas, non-monumental archaeological places. The specific aim is to boost economic, social and cultural

development in these places through innovative and digital practices, avoiding the negative effects of uncontrolled touristic development.

The potential for development is not limited to the Pilots included in the project. Learning and networking is open also to other stakeholders and regions in Europe. In the same way, the analytical findings and policy recommendations are expected to be useful for developing strategies and policies at different scales, sharing relevant datasets, and including the use of structural funds at European level.

Project's findings and results are shared through the project's blog [9] hosted on *digitalmeetsculture* magazine and the YouTube channel [10]. A programme of open workshops, a final conference in Granada and a wide range of dissemination of materials is offered to the INCULTUM targets, including the production of a book. The project's official website offers access to information, news and resources developed within the project and it is the point of departure for the creation of a network of stakeholders in innovative cultural tourism.

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